

The cytoplasmic tail of myelin protein zero induces morphological changes in lipid membranes

Oda C. Krokengen^a, Christine Touma^b, Anna Mularski^c, Aleksi Sutinen^b, Ryan Dunkel^a, Marie Ytterdal^a, Arne Raasakka^a, Haydyn D.T. Mertens^d, Adam Cohen Simonsen^c, Petri Kursula^{a,b,*}

^a Department of Biomedicine, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway

^b Faculty of Biochemistry and Molecular Medicine & Biocenter Oulu, University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland

^c Department of Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark

^d European Molecular Biology Laboratory EMBL, Hamburg Site, c/o DESY, Hamburg, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Myelin
Lipid membrane
Peripheral membrane protein
Protein-membrane interaction
Structure

ABSTRACT

The major myelin protein expressed by the peripheral nervous system Schwann cells is protein zero (P0), which represents 50% of the total protein content in myelin. This 30-kDa integral membrane protein consists of an immunoglobulin (Ig)-like domain, a transmembrane helix, and a 69-residue C-terminal cytoplasmic tail (P0ct). The basic residues in P0ct contribute to the tight packing of myelin lipid bilayers, and alterations in the tail affect how P0 functions as an adhesion molecule necessary for the stability of compact myelin. Several neurodegenerative neuropathies are related to P0, including the more common Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease (CMT) and Dejerine-Sottas syndrome (DSS) as well as rare cases of motor and sensory polyneuropathy. We found that high P0ct concentrations affected the membrane properties of bicelles and induced a lamellar-to-inverted hexagonal phase transition, which caused bicelles to fuse into long, protein-containing filament-like structures. These structures likely reflect the formation of semicrystalline lipid domains with potential relevance for myelination. Not only is P0ct important for stacking lipid membranes, but time-lapse fluorescence microscopy also shows that it might affect membrane properties during myelination. We further describe recombinant production and low-resolution structural characterization of full-length human P0. Our findings shed light on P0ct effects on membrane properties, and with the successful purification of full-length P0, we have new tools to study the role of P0 in myelin formation and maintenance *in vitro*.

1. Introduction

The myelin sheath is an electrical insulator in our nerves. This firmly wrapped multi-layered proteolipid membrane can generate conduction velocities of up to 150 m/s in myelinated axons [1,2]. Integral and peripheral membrane proteins found in myelin that can stack lipid bilayers include proteolipid protein (PLP) [3], peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22) [4], myelin basic protein (MBP) [5–7], myelin protein zero (P0) [8–12], and peripheral myelin protein 2 (P2) [13–15]. P0 corresponds to 50% of total myelin protein in the peripheral nervous system (PNS), and various point mutations in human P0 result in demyelinating peripheral neuropathies, such as Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease (CMT) type 1B, Dejerine-Sottas syndrome, and congenital hypomyelination [16,17].

P0 is the only PNS myelin glycoprotein that spans and compacts both the major dense line (MDL; cytoplasmic apposition) and the intraperiod line (IPL; extracellular apposition). The *shiverer* mouse, which carries a spontaneous MBP knockout, maintains a functionally normal PNS [18]. This suggests that P0 can maintain myelin compaction in the absence of MBP. P0 is not only required during the onset of myelin formation, but also myelin maintenance at a later age, and it is sufficient for myelin compaction [19]. P0 has a low expression level in Schwann cells that do not myelinate compared to myelinating Schwann cells [20], and in non-neuronal cells overexpressing P0, cell-cell adhesion can be observed [21]. Thus, P0 is integral to myelin formation and, consequently, the optimal functioning of the nervous system.

Since the discovery of P0, there has been little understanding of the details of its molecular involvement in myelin compaction. This 30-kDa transmembrane (TM) protein consists of an immunoglobulin (Ig)-like

* Corresponding author at: Department of Biomedicine, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway.

E-mail address: petri.kursula@uib.no (P. Kursula).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamem.2024.184368>

Received 26 March 2024; Received in revised form 24 June 2024; Accepted 1 July 2024

Available online 4 July 2024

0005-2736/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abbreviations

PLP	proteolipid protein	SEC	size exclusion chromatography
PMP22	peripheral myelin protein 22	DMPC	dimyristoyl phosphatidylcholine
MBP	myelin basic protein	DMPG	dimyristoyl phosphatidylglycerol
P0	myelin protein zero	DPC	dodecyl phosphocholine
P0ct	P0 cytoplasmic tail	DOPC	1,2-dioleoyl- <i>sn</i> -glycero-3-phosphocholine
P2	myelin protein 2	DOPS	1,2-dioleoyl- <i>sn</i> -glycero-3-phospho- <i>L</i> -serine
PNS	peripheral nervous system	CD	circular dichroism
CNS	central nervous system	SRCD	synchrotron radiation CD
CMT	Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease	SAXD	small-angle X-ray diffraction
MDL	major dense line	SAXS	small-angle X-ray scattering
IPL	intraprotein line	DPCP	1,2-dicaproyl- <i>sn</i> -glycero-3-phosphocholine
TM	transmembrane	CHAPSO	3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propanesulfonate
Ig	immunoglobulin	SUV	small unilamellar vesicle
MaBP	maltose-binding protein	hP0	full-length human P0

domain, a single TM helix, and a 69-residue C-terminal cytoplasmic tail (P0ct) [22]. The extracellular domain is suggested to homotypically interact in a 'head-to-head' arrangement, and an N-linked oligosaccharide at position 122 is hypothesised to be responsible for the correct orientation of the entire TM glycoprotein, such that the P0 extracellular domains are optimally positioned to dimerise within the IPL [23]. Cryo-EM experiments on reconstituted full-length P0 isolated from bovine nerves revealed a zipper-like arrangement of the Ig-like domains at the extracellular apposition [10], providing a low-resolution model for the PNS IPL. The basic residues in P0ct contribute to the tight packing of the inner leaflets of myelin lipid bilayers, and alterations in P0ct affect the function of P0 as an adhesion molecule in compact myelin [11,12].

Human P0ct carries 21 basic and six acidic residues, giving it a strong positive charge (+15) [24]. This short segment mediates the compaction of the Schwann cell cytoplasm and contributes to the formation of the PNS myelin MDL [25]. P0 contains three cysteine residues; Cys182 is conserved in P0ct, being located at the junction between the TM domain and the tail [26]. Cys182 undergoes palmitoylation, which is important for P0 adhesion. A mutation at this site results in a loss of membrane binding and protein stability [12,27,28]. Most CMT mutations found in P0 affect the Ig-like domain and protein polarity, consequently affecting myelin morphology and Schwann cell-axonal interactions [25,29]. Disease mutations in P0ct have been identified [30–37], suggesting that this highly disordered region is important in myelin membrane compaction.

P0ct is unfolded in aqueous solution, but it gains secondary structure upon lipid interactions. It was first suggested to fold into β -strands, but more recent studies have shown an α -helical conformation for membrane-bound P0ct [9,10,38]. In X-ray diffraction studies, Bragg peaks emerge in a concentration-dependent manner when P0ct is mixed with small unilamellar lipid vesicles [10], indicating the P0ct-induced formation of ordered membrane multilayers with a well-defined repeat distance. Despite its physicochemical similarity to MBP, however, the effects of P0ct on lipid membranes differ from those of MBP [5,9,10]. P0ct causes less membrane stacking than MBP and rather appears to cause liposome fusion into larger structures [9,10].

Different membrane-mimicking model systems exist for investigating membrane protein structure and function in a lipid environment. For many years, these model membranes have predominantly been monolayers and liposomes [39–42], but bicelles have been increasingly used to study membrane proteins. Bicelles were originally developed for NMR studies [43] but have been adapted to other methods, as they may bridge the gap between liposomes and the native flat bilayers found in organisms. While liposomes are spherical, bicelles are flat discs with a rim of detergent [44]. Such nanomembranes are important tools to study the functions and properties of membrane proteins, as information can

be extracted using different techniques, such as X-ray crystallography [45,46], cryo-EM [47,48], small-angle X-ray and neutron scattering [49,50], atomic force microscopy [51,52], and X-ray diffraction [13].

Our previous work on the myelin protein P2 [13] implied that bicelle-based systems provide an interesting membrane model system alternative for studying myelin proteins and their interactions with lipid membranes. Here, we investigated the function of P0ct, while also examining the implications of using bicelles as a myelin-mimetic membrane. Expanding on our previous studies on P0ct and liposomes [9,10], bicelles affect protein-lipid interactions, providing new information about the dynamics of P0ct in the myelin sheath. We report the first instance of full-length human P0 (hP0) expressed and purified recombinantly from insect cells and present a low-resolution structural model for full-length hP0 in detergent micelles. The data provide novel insights into myelin protein-lipid interactions and provide starting points for new lines of study, including myelin protein-induced lipid phase transitions and high-resolution structures of full-length P0 and its disease variants.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Expression and purification of P0ct

P0ct was expressed as a fusion protein with an N-terminal His₆ tag and maltose-binding protein (MaBP). The cloning, expression, and purification of His-MaBP-P0ct have been described previously [10]. Briefly, His-MaBP-P0ct was expressed in *Escherichia coli* BL21(DE3) using 0.4 mM IPTG induction for 3 h in LB medium containing 100 μ g/ml ampicillin, at +37 °C with shaking at 180 rpm. After expression, the cells were collected by centrifugation and resuspended in 40 mM Tris-HCl, 400 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, pH 8.5 with the addition of EDTA-free protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche). The cells were then lysed using ultrasonication and clarified by centrifugation, and the supernatant was collected before continuing the purification by Ni-NTA and amylose affinity chromatography. Elution from the Ni-NTA affinity matrix was performed using 32 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 320 mM NaCl, 500 mM imidazole, before dialysis against 20 mM Tris-HCl, 400 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT, pH 8.5, at +4 °C. Recombinant TEV protease was used for His-MaBP tag removal. Cleaved P0ct was separated from the cleaved tag and the uncleaved protein using amylose affinity chromatography. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) using a HiLoad Superdex 75 pg 16/60 column (GE Healthcare) was used to separate the cleaved protein from any contaminants, resulting in a peak corresponding to pure monodisperse P0ct. The SEC buffer consisted of 20 mM HEPES and 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.5.

2.2. Production of hPO bacmid

Recombinant bacmid production was carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions (Bac-to-Bac System, Life Technologies). Competent *E. coli* DH10Bac cells were transformed with 1 ng of pFastBac Dual hPO-GFP-6xHis (Invitrogen; a TEV cleavage site exists between hPO and its C-terminal tags). The correct isolate was selected using LB plates containing 40 µg/ml Blue-gal, 10 µg/ml tetracycline, 50 µg/ml kanamycin, 7.5 µg/ml gentamycin, and 40 µg/ml IPTG, and the plates were incubated for 48 h at +37 °C. A white colony was selected and restreaked onto a fresh plate and left overnight at +37 °C. A single white colony was selected for growth in liquid LB culture containing the aforementioned antibiotics and used to purify the bacmid using a standard alkaline lysis process. Diagnostic PCR confirmed the transposition of the gene of interest in the bacmid.

2.3. Expression and purification of hPO

Sf9 insect cells cultured in Insect-XPRESS media (Lonza) were transfected with 2 µg of bacmid using the Fugene 6 transfection reagent (Promega), as described by the manufacturer. The medium was supplemented with 10% FCS, 10 U/ml penicillin, and 10 µg/ml streptomycin, and cells were cultured for 7 days at 300 rpm, +27 °C. First-generation baculovirus was harvested by centrifugation and used to infect fresh Sf9 cells in a 1 l suspension culture to induce expression over 3 days at 300 rpm and +27 °C. Expression was monitored using the fluorescence properties of GFP with an excitation peak at 475 nm and an emission peak at 511 nm. hPO-expressing cells were washed with PBS, harvested by centrifugation, flash-frozen in liquid N₂, and stored at -80 °C.

The cell pellets were resuspended in wash buffer (20 mM Tris pH 8.0, 500 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP, 50 mM imidazole), and a douncer was used to rupture the cells. The lysate was ultracentrifuged at 235000 g for 1.5 h, the resulting pellet containing membrane material was resuspended in wash buffer, and a douncer was used for homogenisation. The membrane homogenate was incubated at +4 °C with stirring overnight and supplemented with 1% (w/v) DDM, 20 µg/ml DNase I, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 × protease inhibitor cocktail, and 1 mM TCEP. The homogenate was ultracentrifuged at 235000 g for 1.5 h, and the supernatant was applied onto an equilibrated Ni-NTA slurry and allowed to bind at +4 °C for 1 h. Unbound material was removed, and the matrix was washed with wash buffer supplemented with 0.03% (w/v) DDM. The fusion protein was eluted with elution buffer (20 mM Tris pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP, 500 mM imidazole, 0.03% DDM) and dialysed against SEC buffer (20 mM Tris pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP, 0.03% DDM) at +4 °C overnight in the presence of TEV protease. Reverse IMAC was performed to remove TEV and intact fusion protein. The cleaved hPO was injected into an S200 Increase 10/300 GL column (GE Healthcare), and the peak corresponding to pure monomeric hPO was collected and concentrated using a Vivaspin centrifugal concentrator (Sartorius).

2.4. Vesicle preparation

For all experiments except the membrane patch experiments, dimyristoylphosphatidylcholine (DMPC) and dimyristoylphosphatidylglycerol (DMPG) were purchased from Larodan Fine Chemicals AB (Malmö, Sweden). Lipid stocks were prepared by dissolving the dry lipids in chloroform or chloroform:methanol (75:25) to a final concentration of 10 mg/ml. The solvent was evaporated under a stream of nitrogen gas before freeze-drying overnight at -52 °C under vacuum. The dried lipid mixture was stored air-tight at -20 °C until use.

For the preparation of either liposomes or bicelles, the dried lipids were hydrated with either water or HBS (20 mM HEPES, 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.5) at a final concentration of 5–10 mg/ml, inverting at room temperature overnight to ensure that no unsuspended lipids remained in

the glass vial. The formed multilamellar vesicles (MLVs) were subjected to freeze-thawing using liquid N₂ and a warm water bath with strong vortexing for 30 s. This cycle was repeated 7 times. Small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs) were prepared by sonicating fresh MLVs using a probe-tip sonicator (Branson Model 450, Sonics & Materials Inc. Vibra-cell VC-130) until the lipid suspension was clear, avoiding overheating. Bicelles were prepared by adding *n*-dodecylphosphocholine (DPC) to the MLVs at a q-ratio of 2.84 while pipetting up and down until the solution became clear. The SUVs and bicelles were left at room temperature for at least a couple of hours before use.

For membrane patch experiments, DOPC (1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine) and DOPS (1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phospho-*L*-serine) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, Alabama, USA). Lipid stocks containing DOPC and DOPS were prepared by dissolving dry lipids in methanol (hyper grade for LC-MS, Merck) to a final concentration of 10 mM, with a DOPC:DOPS ratio of 9:1. When the lipids were completely dissolved, 0.05% DiD-C18 probe (Thermo-Invitrogen) was added. The lipid mixture was immediately used to prepare lipid films for patch experiments.

2.5. Membrane patch experiments

Mica substrates (Plano GmbH), glued to glass coverslips using a silicone elastomer (MED-6215, Nusil Technology), were cleaved immediately before use. 50 µl of 10 mM DOPC:DOPS 9:1 (method described above) was applied onto the mica, spun on a spin coater (KW-4A, Chemat Technology) at 150 g for 40 s and placed under vacuum in a desiccator for 10–12 h to ensure solvent evaporation. The spin-coated lipid film was hydrated in 10 mM Tris buffer (2-amino-2-(hydroxymethyl)propane-1,3-diol), 140 mM NaCl, 2 mM Ca²⁺, pH 7.4), for ≥1 h at +60 °C before performing buffer-exchange >10 times to prepare defined secondary bilayer patches. The hydrated membrane patches were cooled to room temperature (+22 °C) and equilibrated for at least 1 h before the experiments.

The response of bilayer patches to the addition of myelin proteins was monitored with time-lapse *epi*-fluorescence microscopy using a Nikon Ti2-E inverted microscope with a 40× objective (Nikon ELWD S Plan Fluor, NA = 0.6). Fluorescence excitation at 550 nm was achieved using a white light fluorescence illumination system (CoolLED, pE-300). Emission was measured at 640 nm (Nikon Cy5-A, M376571). Images were captured at 10 fps with a digital CMOS camera (ORCA-Flash 4.0 V3, Hamamatsu, 2048 × 2044 pixels) using the NIS-Elements software (Nikon). At least three experiments were performed for each condition. For each experiment, P0ct were added to the fluid cell from a known concentrated solution, such that the final bulk concentration was 10 µM.

2.6. Synchrotron radiation circular dichroism spectroscopy

P0ct was dialyzed into Milli-Q water before the SRCD measurements to exclude absorption effects from the buffer components. Protein alone was measured at 0.4 mg/ml in a 100-µm pathlength closed cylindrical cell (Suprasil, Hellma Analytics). SUVs and bicelles (DMPC:DMPG at ratios of 1:1, 4:1, and 9:1) were hydrated in Milli-Q water and prepared as described above. Samples containing lipids were prepared immediately before measurements by mixing P0ct at 0.4 mg/ml to final molar protein-to-lipid ratios (P/L) of 1:50, 1:100, 1:200, and 1:500 with either SUVs or bicelles. Spectra were recorded from 170 to 280 nm at 30 °C. The baseline was subtracted from each dataset before converting the CD units to Δε (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), using the P0ct concentration determined from the absorbance at 280 nm. The measurements were performed several times to ensure reproducibility. SRCD data were collected on the AU-CD beamline at the ASTRID2 synchrotron (ISA, Aarhus, Denmark). Thermal melting of P0ct in solution and with two different ratios of bicelles (P/L 1:50 and 1:100) was performed at temperatures ranging from +24 to +84 °C at roughly 5 °C intervals. Six scans were performed at each temperature, with an equilibration time of 5 min. After reaching the

maximum temperature, 6 more scans were done at +24.2 °C to check for refolding. Melting temperature (T_m) was obtained by fitting the SRCD data at 222 nm to a sigmoidal model (GraphPad Prism 9).

2.7. Stopped-flow SRCD

An SX-20 stopped-flow instrument (Applied Photophysics) mounted on the AU-rSRCD branch line of the AU-AMO beamline at ASTRID2 (ISA, Aarhus, Denmark) was used for data collection at 10 °C. Measurements of 0.1 mg/ml P0ct and DMPC:DMPG (1:1) bicelles at P/L of 1:100 and 1:200 were achieved using a mixer (2 ms dead time) before injecting the sample into the measurement cell (160 μ l total volume, 2-mm path-length) per shot. The CD signal (mdeg) was collected at a fixed wavelength of 195/196 nm for 5 s with 5–10 repeat shots per sample, which were averaged into a single curve. Each sample was prepared in duplicate, and water baselines were subtracted from the sample data. Data were fitted to different exponential functions using GraphPad Prism 9 (Supplementary Table 1).

2.8. Transmission electron microscopy

P0ct was mixed with DMPC:DMPG (1:1) SUVs or bicelles in HBS to final P/L of 1:50, 1:100, and 1:200 before incubating for 1 h at room temperature. 4 μ l of sample were added to a carbon-coated copper grid (300–200 mesh) before incubating for 1 min. The excess solution was removed with filter paper (Whatman), and the sample was stained with 2% uranyl acetate for 12 s. Excess liquid was removed before air-drying. TEM imaging was performed using a Jeol JEM-1230 instrument (Med-WOW). The samples were prepared in duplicate and images were obtained from several locations on the grid.

2.9. Small-angle X-ray diffraction

SAXD experiments were performed to investigate repetitive structures. 30 μ M or 60 μ M P0ct was mixed with SUVs or bicelles containing 3 mM DMPC:DMPG (1:1) in HBS at room temperature and exposed to X-rays on the CoSAXS beamline, MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University (Lund, Sweden) [53]. Lipid samples without P0ct showed no Bragg peaks. The energy was fixed at 12.4 keV with a wavelength of 1.0 Å. The exposure time was 200 ms, and 300 frames were collected for each sample under a continuous flow. Data were processed and analysed using the ATSAS package [54]. The peak position of momentum transfer (s) in the P0ct-lipid samples was used to calculate the repeat distances (d) in the proteolipid structures using Eq. (1):

$$d = \frac{2\pi}{s}, \text{ where } s = \frac{4\pi \sin\theta}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

The membrane thickness of the protein-free liposomes and bicelles was determined using a modified Kratky-Porod (MKP) analysis. Is^4 was plotted against s and fitted with a 4th-order polynomial, and $d_{m,MKP}$ was calculated using Eq. (2) [55]:

$$d_{m,MKP} = \frac{2\pi}{s_{max}} \quad (2)$$

2.10. Small-angle X-ray scattering

SEC-SAXS data were collected from 0.94 mg/ml of hP0 in 20 mM Tris pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP, 0.03% DDM at Diamond Light Source beamline B21 (Harwell Science & Innovation Campus, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom) [56] and 14.4 mg/ml of P0ct in HBS on the CoSAXS beamline, MAX IV laboratory (Lund, Sweden). See Supplementary Table 2 for further details. Data collected from P0ct were processed and analysed using ATSAS [54]. Ensemble optimisation analysis was performed using EOM [57] and *ab initio* modelling with GASBOR [58].

The hP0 model was finalised in CORAL [59]. Restraints were set to

the TM helix, whereas the N- and C-terminal domains were flexible. A hinge was present between the Ig domain and the TM, and the P0ct was built by the software. 100 DDM molecules were added around the TM helix using CHARMM-GUI [60]. Visualization was carried out in PyMOL [61]. AlphaFold2 [62] was run on the Google ColabFold server [63], where the input was the amino acid sequence of full-length human P0 and P0ct (UniProt ID: P25189).

Density maps were modelled in RAW 2.1.4 [64] using the DENSS electron density map feature [65]. Twenty reconstructions were performed with a default set of 10,000 electrons. Each density was aligned and averaged before the final refinement. Symmetry constraints were not applied. The refined electron density map was visualized using PyMOL [61].

3. Results

3.1. Liposome and bicelle characterisation

Liposomes and bicelles used to investigate P0ct were prepared from DMPC and DMPG, using DPC as a detergent for the bicelles. These membrane-mimicking model systems can be easily prepared, and different buffers can be used if necessary. The membrane thickness (d_m , MKP) was calculated using the MKP method [55,66] for samples collected at RT from several SAXS beamtimes. Following the calculations by Hägerbäumer et al. [55], $I(s) \cdot s^4$ was plotted against s , before fitting the plots to a fourth-order polynomial (Fig. 1A). The SAXS curves of both model systems exhibited a typical broad peak characteristic of a phospholipid bilayer structure. The $d_{m,MKP}$ was calculated from the maximal s -value using Eq. (2). The sonicated liposomes had a wider span of membrane thickness than bicelles, with a mean thickness of 37.64 Å, when data were collected over several beamtimes (Fig. 1B). The mean membrane thickness for the liposomes was larger than that reported previously [55,66] for pure DMPC liposomes prepared by extrusion. Sonication gives liposomes of a more variable size, and the deviation is expected to be higher than that in a more homogenous sample of extruded vesicles; in addition, DMPG influences the membrane thickness. Additional variation may arise because the experimental temperature was close to that of the dimyristoyl lipid phase transition.

The mean membrane thickness for bicelles in this study was 34.75 Å at a q-ratio of 2.84 (Fig. 1B). DMPC bicelles with 1,2-dicaproyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPCP) had a membrane thickness ranging from 36 to 40 Å with a q-ratio of 3.5 [67], whereas bicelles with a mix of DMPC and DMPG with 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propanesulfonate (CHAPSO) (q = 3.0) had a thickness of 51 Å [68]. In DMPG, the choline headgroup of DMPC is replaced by glycerol, resulting in a net negative charge. The q-ratio mostly determines the diameter of the bicelles [69], but thickness also depends on the q-ratio [70]. Moreover, doping bicelles with negatively charged lipids, such as DMPG, results in more rigid membranes [71]. Consequently, using 50% DMPG may explain the decrease in membrane thickness in these bicelles compared with pure DMPC-DPCP/DHPC bicelles or DMPC:DMPG-DHPC bicelles, in which the fraction of DMPG is lower [70]. Importantly, the variation in membrane thickness between measurements was much less for bicelles than liposomes, indicating a more homogeneous population and high reproducibility. Hence, bicelles were further tested as a lipid model system for myelin protein-membrane interactions.

To complement the membrane thickness analysis and control the formation of liposomes and bicelles, we visualized the samples using TEM (Fig. 1C). Sonicated liposomes are expected to be spherical and to vary more in size than extruded liposomes, whereas bicelles should form when DPC is added to the MLVs - the vesicles should flatten, and the rims of the discs will be lined with detergent. TEM images revealed poly-disperse vesicles and bicelles with little to no aggregation. These results confirm the homogeneous nature of the bicelle population, in line with the X-ray scattering analysis above. Both membrane-mimicking systems resemble previously published data [10,13] and were used to study the

Fig. 1. Characterisation of bicelles and sonicated liposomes. A) Membrane thickness ($d_{m,MKP}$) was calculated using the MKP method [55]; $I(s) \cdot s^4$ was plotted against s before fitting the plot with a fourth-order polynomial. The maximal s -value was determined and membrane thickness calculated using Eq. (2), $d_{m,MKP}$ denoted in the upper right corner. Measurements were performed at room temperature. B) $d_{m,MKP}$ from four separate measurements of liposomes (black) and bicelles (blue) at different time points on the MAX IV Lund CoSAXS beamline. The mean value is shown as a line. C) Visualization of the two mimicking model systems using TEM with an illustration to clarify (middle). Liposomes (left) are round spheres, whereas bicelles (right) are flat disks. Scale bar, 100 nm. Control TEM images of buffer and protein are shown in Supplementary Fig. 1.

protein-lipid interactions of P0ct.

3.2. Secondary structure of P0ct in membrane-mimetic models

Folding investigations of P0ct have previously been performed using liposomes, but not bicelles. Earlier experiments revealed a high α -helical content in various vesicle lipid mixtures and detergents [9,10]. In the present study, the overall findings were as expected; P0ct was unfolded in water and gained helical secondary structure when interacting with the lipid models.

To investigate the effect of negatively charged lipids on the secondary structure of P0ct, various lipid mixtures were prepared (10%, 25%, and 50% DMPG) at P/L ratios of 1:50, 1:100, 1:200, and 1:500 (Supplementary Fig. 3). Over the various P/L ratios, the 50% DMPG liposomes and bicelles (DMPC:DMPG 1:1) seemed to be the most favourable for secondary structure formation, with a high intensity of the positive peak at 190 nm and two negative peaks at around 208 and 220 nm. P0ct favours negatively charged lipids, and the quantity of DMPG influences the degree of folding. The PNS myelin cytosolic leaflet is negatively charged, and the membrane has a high lipid-to-protein ratio (70–85% lipid by mass compared with 15–30% protein), which contributes to the close packing of the myelin sheath [72]. This mirrors what was observed in the SRCD measurement, as a high negatively charged lipid content facilitated secondary structure formation in P0ct (Supplementary Fig. 3). In Fig. 2A, all P/L ratios are shown with lipid mimetics containing 50% DMPG, and the difference in CD amplitude reflects the amount of aggregation of large particles, while the movement of the CD minimum peak from 200 nm towards higher wavelengths, concomitantly with a stronger band at 195 and 220 nm, is a sign

of an increased helical structure. The maximal level of folding seemed to be reached at a P/L ratio of 1:100, and increasing the lipid amount above this level no longer induced changes in the CD peak positions. At a P/L ratio of 1:50, P0ct was less folded than at a P/L ratio of 1:100, which could reflect crowding on the membrane surface. Changing the model system did not have a large effect on the secondary structure of P0ct, except for a slight increase in the intensity of the peaks when bicelles were used, most likely reflecting less aggregation. Folding of P0ct might be facilitated by flattening of the model system, potentially providing the required membrane curvature and a larger contact area for van der Waals interactions necessary for helical folding of membrane proteins [73–76].

3.3. Bicelles aggregate more slowly than liposomes

The kinetics of the initial P0ct-induced bicelle aggregation were measured using stopped-flow SRCD, as previously established [77] (Fig. 2B). P0ct and bicelles were measured separately, revealing flat kinetics, which suggested no vesicle fusion or aggregation in the isolated samples. However, when mixed at two different P/L ratios, a strong decay was observed within a 5-s time frame. All samples proved reproducible between shots and replicates, displaying a good overlay. The details of the two-phase decay parameters can be found in Supplementary Table 1. The P0ct-bicelle sample data could be fitted using two rate constants: k_1 , describing a fast event ($> 2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), and k_2 , for a slower event ($< 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [77]. At P/L of 1:100, k_1 is more than doubled compared to P/L of 1:200, while the slower rate constant is in a similar range (P/L 1:100 $k_2 = 0.98 \text{ s}^{-1}$, P/L 1:200 $k_2 = 0.58 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Hence, P0ct induces faster turbidity when less lipids are present. With liposomes, the P/L ratio

Fig. 2. SRCD experiments. A) The folding of P0ct in the two models (DMPC:DMPG 1:1) was studied using SRCD with different P/L ratios. Additional spectra of various lipid mixtures are presented in Supplementary Fig. 3. B) Stopped-flow kinetics of bicelle aggregation. The SRCD signal at 195–200 nm was monitored for 5 s by stopped-flow measurements. P0ct was measured in the absence and presence of bicelles at two protein-to-lipid ratios using 150 mM NaF. The rate constants k_1 and k_2 for P/L 1:100 and P/L 1:200 are shown in the inset. See Supplementary Table 1 for all the rate constants and Supplementary Fig. 2 for the log spectra. C) Thermal measurements were performed on three samples with temperatures ranging from +24 to +84 °C: P0ct in solution (left), P/L 1:50 (middle), and P/L 1:100 (right). Bicelles were used as the membrane model.

1:200 had a k_1 of 20.14 s^{-1} and a k_2 of 1.12 s^{-1} [9,77]. Why the differences in k_1 between the two model systems are so substantial is not known, but the results suggest that the initial aggregation of liposomes happens at a faster rate than for the bicelles. This difference may be attributed to larger interacting surface areas.

3.4. P0ct keeps its folding at high temperatures

In our earlier studies, myelin protein P2 remained folded in DMPC:DMPG liposomes up to +90 °C [78]. In the absence of lipids, P2 denatures completely at $\sim +60$ °C [78]. To see if P0ct behaves similarly, samples were subjected to thermal denaturation (Fig. 2C) at +24 to +80 °C, followed by a final measurement after re-cooling back to +24 °C. In the absence of lipids, P0ct aggregates as the temperature rises, as evident from the decreasing CD signal intensity (apparent T_m +57.9 °C). In the bicelle-containing samples, secondary structure is prominent at +24 °C, and this helical structure is stable for several temperature increments before the signal disappears. High temperatures cause the protein-bicelle clusters to aggregate (apparent T_m +55.0 °C at P/L 1:50 and +61.4 °C at P/L 1:100). P0ct remains helical upon bicelle aggregation at higher temperatures, as the positions of the CD peaks do not change. Consequently, the melting temperatures obtained from these experiments are an indication of sample aggregation rather than the actual process of protein unfolding.

3.5. High concentrations of P0ct fuse membranes instead of stacking

TEM was used to visualize the effects of P0ct on the different lipid models. At the lowest P/L ratios of either SUVs or bicelles, P0ct induces lipid aggregates differently in the two membrane-mimicking systems. With the highest concentration of P0ct (P/L 1:50), liposomes form what

resembles membrane sheets (Fig. 3A, upper row), suggesting a fusion of the free liposomes seen in control samples (Fig. 1C). Similar observations, with very large continuous lipid structures induced by P0ct, have been previously observed [9,10]. This is different from MBP, which includes strong stacking of membranes into multilayers [5]. From several of the sheets, one can see “membrane tails” protruding from the merged vesicles. This suggests that the protein is used up in the formation of the larger lipid structures, leaving some liposomes in an unfused state. At increasing lipid content, these sheets are no longer visible; instead, clusters of vesicles can be seen. In the vesicle control sample, the vesicles are seen freely on the grid, while at P/L 1:100, some vesicles are still free in solution, but a larger amount is aggregated together in variable-sized assemblies. The same is true for P/L 1:200, although more free vesicles are observed.

When using bicelles, the aggregates formed by P0ct appear different. In contrast to the membrane sheets, bicelles with the same concentration of P0ct (P/L 1:50) fuse into long filament-like structures (Fig. 3A, lower row). Visually, there is a large difference in the appearance of the membrane-mimicking systems, when P0ct is added at high concentrations. The formation of filaments is lost when more lipids are present (P/L 1:100). The bicelles appear to be aggregated more randomly, and at P/L 1:200, stacks of bicelles can be observed.

For both lipid models, when the concentration of P0ct is high enough, either vesicles or bicelles merge, forming larger, relatively flat lipid structures. The membranes may be saturated with the protein in this case, which prevents their stacking. Similar conclusions were earlier drawn based on atomic force microscopy experiments [10]. For higher ratios of lipids, the appearance is more similar, more free lipids are seen when the lipid ratio increases. The results indicate that P0ct can affect lipid membrane morphology in a concentration-dependent manner. Since the above SRCD experiments indicated that at P/L 1:50, P0ct is less

Fig. 3. Effect of P0ct on membrane morphology. A) Liposomes on the top row, bicelles on the bottom row, at 3 different P/L ratios. P0ct fuses lipid particles differently depending on the membrane model and P/L ratio; P/L 1:50 assembles uniquely. With liposomes, P0ct induces sheath-like structures with protruding lipid “tail”, while the protein fuses bicelles into filamentous threads. Control TEM images are shown in Supplementary Fig. 1. Scale bars are set to 100 nm. B) Fluorescence patch experiment. 10 μ M of P0ct was added to DOPC:DOPS (9:1, 0.05% DiD—C18) and visualized for 15 min. Before adding protein (0 s), the patches and the lipid bilayer underneath are intact. The addition of P0ct induces cavities in the underlying lipid layers and accumulation of lipids in the developed gaps (bright spots). This formation was not observed in bilayer controls (not shown). Original movies of the experiment are shown in Supplementary Movies 1–2.

folded than at P/L 1:100, it appears that the membrane has reached saturation of its capacity to bind P0ct and induce its folding.

3.6. P0ct alters membrane morphology

Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy was used to further investigate the P0ct-lipid interactions on planar supported bilayers. Bilayers of DOPC and DOPS were prepared with a DOPC:DOPS ratio of 9:1, and 0.05% DiD-C18 probe was added to the lipid mixture as a fluorescent marker. Before the addition of P0ct, the supported bilayers formed double bilayer islands, without measurable malformations (Fig. 3B, 0 s). The effects of P0ct addition were recorded for approximately 15 min. With time, the fluorescent bilayers become bleached by the prolonged light exposure. The first indication of P0ct influencing the bilayers appeared after \sim 2 min. The first consequence of P0ct addition is the manifestation of holes/cavities in the primary bilayer (darkest shaded bilayer). These holes may be a sign of membrane condensation induced by P0ct, decreasing the area per lipid molecule. With time, more cavities are observed, and bright spots emerge at the edges of the holes (black arrows in Fig. 3B), indicating the formation of new lipid structures. Over 15 min, the cavities grow, and more lipids accumulate at the edges. Bilayers without protein were filmed as control, but no changes in morphology were observed, implying that the changes in membrane structure are induced by P0ct. The lipid accumulation is only observed when there are secondary bilayers. In a similar experiment, myelin protein P2 induced the formation of new membrane structures [15]

without the generation of cavities; thus, the effects of these two PNS myelin MDL proteins on supported lipid bilayers are different.

3.7. Evidence of non-lamellar lipid crystals at high protein concentration

We performed SAXD with liposomes in previous studies on both P0ct and MBP [5,9,10], but did not previously employ bicelles. The first myelin protein-bicelle diffraction experiments were performed with P2 [13], whereby a set of new diffraction peaks were observed upon the addition of P2 protein. The results were interpreted as the formation of semi-crystalline proteolipid structures. With liposomes, the typical peak induced by P0ct at around 70–75 Å is visible with its second-order peak, indicating ordered lamellar stacking (Fig. 4A-B, black lines). The same repeat distance has been observed in previous work and is relatively consistent between measurements and protein concentrations [9,10]. The 75 Å repeat distance corresponds to the thickness of cytoplasmic stacks in myelin (two cytoplasmic membrane leaflets and the protein phase in between) and is in the same range as reported for P2 and MBP [5,13,79]. For liposomes, the membrane thickness was measured to be 37.7 Å (Fig. 1), and the lamellar periodicity was 73.8 Å and 75.3 Å for P/L 1:100 and P/L 1:50, respectively (Fig. 4C). This denotes that the water gap, containing P0ct, between the bilayers is 36.2 Å and 38.2 Å for the two concentrations of P0ct; a higher concentration of P0ct increases the intermembrane distance. Changing the concentration of P0ct does not change the number of diffraction peaks seen in the experiment, but the narrowing of the peaks indicates a higher degree of order in the repeating units [80]. Liposomes have for a long time been the go-to model system in diffraction experiments, but using bicelles for these types of measurements is a good source of complementary information on how the proteins are arranged within a membrane system [13].

Up to eight X-ray diffraction peaks were observed for the highest P0ct concentration when bicelles were used as the biomimetic analogue (Fig. 4A-B, blue lines). No Bragg peaks were observed for P0ct alone or in complex with DPC detergent (Supplementary Fig. 4). Three peaks appeared at around 76.2, 68.7, and 54.4 Å with 30 μ M of P0ct (P/L 1:100). In contrast, P/L of 1:50 revealed eight peaks corresponding to 78.9, 72.5, 69.3, 55.9, 41.5, 39.4, 36.3, and 33.2 Å. The presumed lamellar d-spacing of P/L 1:100 is 76.2 Å (peak 1), while the two additional peaks, labelled x_1 (68.70 Å) and x_2 (54.40 Å), did not fit a lamellar peak ratio of 1:2:3:4. The lamellar repeat distance in the bicelle system was therefore \sim 3 Å larger than in the liposome system. The mean membrane thickness of the bicelles ($d_{m, MKP}$) was estimated to be 34.8 Å; thus, the water gap was 41.4 Å for P/L 1:100, an apparent increase of 5.2 Å compared to the liposome sample (an increase of 6.0 Å for P/L 1:50); however, the large variability in the liposome membrane thickness should be considered. The peak pattern for P/L 1:50 corresponds best to the presence of a hexagonal lattice system (Fig. 4D). Two positions of the first-order lamellar peak 1 (blue and red labels in Fig. 4B) reveal several peak ratios matching a hexagonal system, potentially mixed with a lamellar phase (Fig. 4B, blue and red respectively). Regardless of the peak 1 position, there are peaks not fitting to any lattice system tested, marked with y_{1-4} . For both bicelle samples, the unidentified peaks (x_{1-2} , y_{1-4}) give evidence that unidentified non-lamellar phases occur within the bicelle cluster, collectively with the lamellar d-spacing and the hexagonal lattice system. Taken together, when mixed with liposomes, P0ct induces lamellar stacking of the membranes, while in the bicelle system, a mixture of lipid phases is observed. The mixture may be a sign of an evolving system, and different incubation times for such a complex could give more insight into the endpoint of the process.

3.8. Purification and initial characterisation of recombinant human full-length P0

The cytoplasmic tail of P0 has been extensively studied, while hP0 has not been purified for structural studies before. P0ct can be produced

Fig. 4. X-ray diffraction of P0ct with SUVs and bicelles. A-B) Adding 30 or 60 μM P0ct to liposomes (black lines) results in two major Bragg peaks, while the same concentration added to bicelles (blue lines) gives three or more Bragg peaks. Peak numbered with 1 indicates lamellar d-spacing. B) Blue and red labels for each peak reflect two approaches to analyzing the Bragg peaks. The curves have been offset for clarity. C) The mean repeat distances, calculated from the s -values corresponding to the intensity summit of each Bragg peak, going from left to right corresponding to the peaks seen in A-B. One repeat distance is indicated for each liposome sample as the second peak is the second order and not a repeat distance by itself. D) Illustration of the main liquid crystal systems; the lamellar Bragg peak position ratio of 1:2:3:4:5... and the ratios of hexagonal lattice and hexagonal closed packed systems.

recombinantly in *E. coli*, whereas hP0 is a greater challenge, as membrane proteins are in general difficult to purify and require detergent to remain in solution [81]. We expressed and purified hP0 using insect cells and a cleavable GFP tag. DDM was found to be a suitable detergent to obtain reasonable amounts of pure protein. In short, the membrane homogenate was incubated with DDM to solubilize hP0, and IMAC was executed before and after cleavage of the tag, before a final SEC step to obtain pure protein. Mass spectrometry was employed on the final product to verify the correct protein.

The Ig-like domain of P0 has been crystallized and characterized at high resolution [22,82], while biophysical characterization has been done for P0ct [9,10,38,77,83]. Consequently, this key protein of PNS myelin has only been studied in parts, and no experimental information on full-length P0 exists, apart from low-resolution electron cryo-micrographs of liposome-reconstituted P0 purified from bovine nerves and reconstituted into liposomes [10]. Since more experiments are required to fully understand P0 function in myelin, we present the first structural characterization of recombinant hP0 (Fig. 5). SEC-SAXS data were acquired for hP0 in DDM micelles; SEC facilitated the separation of empty micelles from protein-detergent complexes. SAXS data for hP0 can be seen in Fig. 5A, and from the normalized Kratky plot, hP0 appears to be folded with flexible domains (Fig. 5B). R_g derived from the SAXS data was $38.83 \pm 0.7 \text{ \AA}$, with a D_{max} of 119.10 nm (Fig. 5C). To obtain a model for the protein-detergent complex based on the SAXS data, several modelling programs were tested; a hybrid model generated in CORAL [59] had the best fit (Fig. 5A,D). An AlphaFold2 [62] model for

hP0 was generated as well as a 3D reconstruction of the electron density from the experimental SAXS data. SEC-SAXS data were also acquired for highly concentrated, pure P0ct (Supplementary Fig. 5) to supplement the findings; an AlphaFold2 model of P0ct has been discussed before [83]. P0ct was elongated and flexible, showing a mixture of more extended and compacted conformations (Supplementary Fig. 5).

In the SAXS-based model of the hP0-DDM complex (Fig. 5D), a detergent belt surrounds the TM helix, while the Ig-like domain and the cytoplasmic tail are placed on opposite sides of the micelle. The SAXS-based model is similar, but not identical, to the AlphaFold2 model. At the C-terminal end, the cytoplasmic tail is modelled as elongated based on SAXS; in the AlphaFold2 model, it turns back towards the TM helix. The AlphaFold2 per-residue confidence score (pLDDT) and the predicted aligned error (PAE) are shown in Supplementary Fig. 6A. Molecular dynamics simulations [84–86] of hP0 similarly conclude with an R_g of 42.8 \AA . A DENSS electron density fit of the SEC-SAXS data is shown in Fig. 5D (fitting of the DENSS map is shown in Supplementary Fig. 6B), indicating an increased volume, showing the DDM micelle around the TM helix. To conclude, modelling of full-length hP0 based on both predictions and SAXS data indicates a folded extracellular domain, a TM helix in a detergent micelle, and a flexible cytoplasmic tail. The dimensions of P0ct in solution indicate that it must obtain a more compact structure when bound between two membranes at the myelin MDL.

Fig. 5. Characterisation of hP0 in DDM. A) SAXS curve and the CORAL fit, B) Kratky plot, and C) distance distribution. D) Hybrid CORAL model of hP0 with DDM molecules (left), AlphaFold2 model of hP0 given only the sequence as input (UniProt ID: P25189) [62] (N-terminal region removed for clarity, cytoplasmic tail encircled) (middle), and a 3D reconstruction of the electron density profile (right).

4. Discussion

Accurate ensheathment of axons depends on several proteins, and the P0 glycoprotein is vital for PNS myelination and myelin compaction [87–89]. As an integral membrane protein, P0 functions as an adhesion protein on both sides of the membrane; it adheres extracellular membrane leaflets together through oligomerization of the Ig-like domains, and on the opposite side, P0ct partially folds and inserts into the inner leaflet [11,28,90,91]. Nonetheless, the P0 molecular mechanism remains a mystery. We previously investigated P2 using bicelles as a membrane model [13] to yield new evidence of myelin structural assembly. Here, we use different membrane mimics in the investigation of P0ct function within the MDL of PNS myelin to shed light on the effects of P0ct on lipid membrane properties. We also present a preliminary structural analysis of full-length human P0.

4.1. Membrane morphology and P0

The overall lipid composition of the myelin membrane is unique and is rich in several lipids, including galactosylceramide and cholesterol [92]. Both of the latter have been characterized to be important for the formation and function of myelin in mammals [93–97]. We understand the simple lipid compositions used in the current study, lacking these key lipid components, will only scratch the surface of the native lipid composition of myelin and specifically its inner leaflet. We opted for using such simple mixtures across the set of experiments, mainly of DMPC/DMPG and DOPC/DOPS for practical reasons, as these mixtures can be reproducibly produced, and they behave well in the line of experiments carried out. Key features of the model systems used are the

controllable level of negative surface charge, based on the level of incorporated DMPG or DOPS, and a phase transition temperature close to room temperature for the dimyristoyl-based lipids, which can be easily studied using DPC. We have shown before that the CD spectrum of P0ct is very similar in DMPC:DMPG and in a native-like lipid mix [10], justifying the current line of experiments in simple models. Future work must be carried out in more native-like systems and combining different myelin proteins.

Another obvious question is the relation of bicelles, which are relatively unstable structures, to events taking place in myelin. Bicelles are flat discs, which may therefore stack easily when myelin proteins are present; these stacks are less opaque than those of liposomes, which allows for more spectroscopic applications. This we saw before with myelin protein P2 [13]. It is likely that the detergent present at the bicelle edges makes the bicelles unstable and allows for easier changes in lipid morphology. We believe this is what is seen here with P0ct when tube-like structures with non-lamellar structures are formed. While this phenomenon may not be relevant for myelination, it does indicate a strong propensity of the proteins present in the PNS myelin MDL to directly affect lipid membrane structure. In the future, longer incubation times for such samples will be useful to follow the development of the membrane structure induced by myelin proteins. Lipid nanodiscs will be another tool for structural studies in the future.

Although liposomes and bicelles differ mostly in shape, it is evident that the model system used has a notable impact on P0ct-lipid interactions. Changing the membrane model does not influence the secondary structure of P0ct, but as visualized in TEM (Fig. 3A), a high concentration of P0ct induces the formation of either sheet- or filament-like structures. Filament structures have been observed with liposomes

at higher P/L ratios [10] but were only observed with bicelles here. The thickness of the filaments was 10–20 nm, matching earlier findings [10]. With either model system, high concentrations of P0ct appear to cause membrane fusion instead of membrane aggregation, which suggests the importance of correct protein concentration for myelin membrane wrapping and stacking. Linked to this observation, at P/L 1:50, P0ct was less folded than at higher lipid concentrations, suggesting a relationship between the P0ct folding state, its concentration on the membrane, and its effect on membrane structure.

Using liposomes, the Bragg peaks indicated the presence of a lamellar structure, with a more ordered structure with the addition of more P0ct (Fig. 4A-B) [9,10]. However, for bicelles, more peaks appear at higher protein concentrations, which cannot be explained with simple lamellar d-spacing (Fig. 4). Amphiphilic lipids can have polymorphism for other phases including hexagonal, bicontinuous cubic, sponge, and discrete micellar phases [98,99], also in complex with other molecules [100]. When comparing various lattice systems, it became apparent that P0ct modulates lipid phase transitions depending on which model system is used, *i.e.* liposomes or bicelles. In the 1980s, Kruijff and Cullis found that both the mitochondrial protein cytochrome C and the attachment factor poly-L-lysine caused hexagonal phase transition in membranes containing certain negatively charged lipids [101,102]. Following either blue or red labels in Fig. 4B, the hexagonal lattice system matches 2–4 peaks induced by P0ct, while two Bragg peaks fit a lamellar lattice [103,104]. The Ig-like domain of P0 is understood to stack membranes in a zipper-like fashion [10,88], but the P0ct mode of binding is not fully known. The basic peptide poly-L-lysine and MBP are both thought to not only affect the membrane surface but also to interact with the hydrophobic tails of the lipids [105,106], increasing the mobility of the lipid alkyl chains [107]. Binding of P0ct leads to thermotropic modifications of lipid membranes [9,10]; in addition, structural alterations appear in bicelle membranes visualized by TEM and confirmed by SAXD. DPC does not cause diffraction peaks on its own (Supplementary Fig. 4), so the lipid phase transition is due to protein-lipid interactions in the model system. Many peaks cannot be explained by simple lamellar or hexagonal lattices; thus, other systems need to be involved as well. There is evidence that cubic phases can be established close to the L-H_{II} phase transition [108], and neutron reflectometry revealed that P0ct inserts into supported DMPC:DMPG lipid bilayers [9]. Consequently, it is feasible that P0ct embeds part of itself close to the core of the bicelle generating the increased movement needed for the phase transition towards hexagonal and other connected lattice systems. Another potential explanation is that the unknown peaks can be attributed to the protein organization within the lipid membranes. Diffraction peaks have been attributed to the organization of MBP bound to multilamellar vesicles [109], and the same can be true for P0ct. Further investigation, using complementary techniques, will be needed to reveal the full mechanism.

Induced hexagonal phase transition has not been studied for P0, but it can be a feature of a disrupted myelin structure potentially relevant for neuropathies associated with P0, as found with other myelin proteins, including MBP, PMP22, and PLP. Shaharabani et al. found that MBP, a major protein in CNS and associated with multiple sclerosis, induced hexagonal phase transition in a disease-like lipid membrane composition [109]. The presence of the hexagonal phase reduced with lowered MBP concentration, indicating a relationship between them; nevertheless, temperature, lipid composition, and salt concentration also affected lipid organization [110]. Like for MBP in either lipid composition, native or disease-like [109], the addition of P0ct reveals several correlation peaks demonstrating enhanced organization of the lipid membranes. Wrabetz et al. studied peripheral nerve myelination in mice concerning the expression of P0. The results revealed a dose-dependent dysmyelinating neuropathy with a threshold for dysmyelination between 30 and 80% overexpression of P0, indicating that normal myelination requires a strictly regulated expression of P0 [111]. This observation may be linked to the different membrane morphologies observed at high concentrations of P0ct here. Dysmyelination has been

observed when overexpressing PLP, causing Pelizaeus-Merzbacher disease [112], and PMP22 overexpression is linked to CMT1A [113]. Although most neuropathies related to P0 involve mutations found in the Ig-like domain or P0ct [8,9,31,33,34,89,114–117], rare cases of increased P0 gene dosage have been reported, in which patients appeared with motor and sensory polyneuropathy [118,119]. A concentration- and folding-dependent effect on lipid membrane properties could, therefore, be studied further as a molecular disease mechanism of de- and dysmyelination.

Having observed the filament-like membrane structures in the TEM images, we propose a potential mechanism for the proteolipid structure (Fig. 6). When P0ct is added to either liposomes or bicelles at lower concentrations, P0ct binds to the membrane and induces lamellar stacking. With high concentrations, when the membrane surface starts to get saturated with protein, the bicelles start to fuse. Simultaneously with the folding of P0ct, the bicelles fuse, establishing longer filaments where “pockets” within the filament contain hexagonal phases, as the Bragg peaks reflect. The filaments do not seem to adhere to each other, which further supports the notion that the protein is enclosed by lipids, as postulated for cytochrome C [102]. Another option is the development of so-called cylindrical micelles through the action of P0ct, as observed earlier for α -synuclein [120].

Fig. 6. Schematic illustration of the potential hexagonal folding of P0ct-bicelle samples. When P0ct is added to bicelles, we propose a potential mechanism for a hexagonal filament induced by P0ct. At lower P/L ratios, most diffraction peaks are consistent with a lamellar lattice for either bicelles or liposomes (far right and left side). At higher protein concentrations, P0ct fuses bicelles, forming longer filaments where a network of “pockets” inside may harbour P0ct (middle).

In myelin, P0 is mainly thought of as an adhesion molecule, but based on TEM and the patch experiments in combination with X-ray diffraction, one can speculate that P0 might be an important factor in the migration of Schwann cell membrane and its elongation along the axon, as postulated by Wrabetz et al. [111]. Not only does P0ct induce a membrane fusion at low P/L ratios, but it also affects membrane properties (Fig. 3B). Annexin A1 and A2 have been reported to induce the formation of double-membrane structures [121,122], which was also shown for myelin protein P2 [15]. For P0ct, holes and lipid accumulations were seen, indicating myelin protein-dependent changes in membrane morphology. The possible membrane-condensing effect observed for P0ct on supported planar membranes, together with its effect on membrane phase transition behaviour observed before [10], may be related to molecular mechanisms of myelin formation. Overall, current data support direct effects by P0ct, as well as other myelin proteins, on lipid membrane structure and properties, and this activity is likely relevant for myelination.

4.2. P0 structure starts to unfold

Even though P0 is recognized as a core building block of PNS myelin, full-length human P0 has not been recombinantly purified before, and a high-resolution structure of hP0 is not available. As a first step towards structural studies on hP0 and its complexes, we reported here the expression, purification, and initial SEC-SAXS characterisation of hP0. A Kratky plot of the SAXS curve shows a folded protein with some flexible domains. hP0 consists of an N-terminal signal sequence (residue 1-29) and three domains; the Ig-like domain (residue 30-153), the TM helix (residue 154-179) and the cytoplasmic tail (residue 180-248); the Ig-like domain is the only one crystallized (rat: PDB ID 1NEU, human: PDB ID 3OAI) [22,82]. Crystallization of the extracellular domain revealed an Ig-like domain comprising ten β -strands arranged as two β -sheets displaying a hydrophobic core featured by the immunoglobulin family [22,82,123]. In the SAXS-based model, a monomeric fraction of hP0 was analysed, and hence, no oligomerisation of the extracellular domain was observed.

The arrangement of the P0 Ig-like domains in the IPL of PNS myelin has been an open question. In our earlier work, cryo-EM revealed a zipper-like arrangement of the Ig-like domains [10], which challenged existing models of the IPL. The conserved residues Arg74 and His81 of the Ig-like domains interact, causing the adhesion needed for a tight compartment [88,124]. Mutations linked to these amino acids, together with several others in the same domain, are linked to reduced P0 function in several types of CMT [8,89,114,125–127].

The last residues at the end of the extracellular domain are disordered and believed to supply flexibility at the membrane surface [82]. 26 residues make up the P0 TM helix, engulfed by a DDM micelle in the model. The helix has a glycine zipper motif (GxxxGxxxG) commonly found in membrane-associated proteins [91,128]. The TM helix undergoes dimerization, which supports oligomerisation of the Ig-like domains on the same membrane [91]. Two mutations associated with CMT (G134R) and Dejerine-Sottas syndrome (G138R) reside within the TM domain, having substantial effects on P0 membrane insertion and dimerization [91].

AlphaFold2 starts the TM helix at the correct residue (Tyr154) but models the TM domain and the cytoplasmic domain as one elongated helix with a short, disordered tail. A segment of the long helix in the AlphaFold2 model (Fig. 5D, black dotted square), in fact, belongs to P0ct based on experimental work. An amphipathic helix is believed to be separated from the TM helix by a small hinge necessary for its flexibility to bind along the membrane surface [21,83]. When P0ct is given as a separate sequence, AlphaFold2 models P0ct to contain helical segments [83], which has been observed experimentally when P0ct is bound to lipid membranes [9,10,77]. How P0ct binds and resides within the MDL of myelin is not fully known. One important detail from the hybrid SAXS-based model is that the cytoplasmic tail is extended and not folded

back onto the DDM micelle and appears to have the flexibility required to bind to a second membrane. If the P0ct folded upon the same micelle, full-length P0 would have a smaller maximum dimension (D_{max}), with dimensions similar to the AlphaFold2 model. The 3D electron density profile modelled with DENSS supports the notion of an elongated conformation of the cytoplasmic tail protruding down from the helix-DDM assembly. The dimensions of the P0ct in solution suggest it must compact extensively to fit at the confined space of the myelin MDL.

4.3. Concluding remarks

P0 is adhesive on both sides of the PNS myelin membrane; a zipper-like assembly of the extracellular domains is accompanied by the intrinsically disordered P0ct in a tight space between two cytoplasmic membrane leaflets. We have provided new information on the interactions of P0ct with lipids, revealing concentration-dependent effects on membrane morphology and lipid phase behaviour. Such phenomena may be relevant when the myelin membrane grows and wraps around the axon, as well as when the multilayered membrane compacts to produce mature myelin. The presence of human disease-linked mutations in the P0ct domain highlights the importance of the interactions of this small, flexible segment with lipid membranes. Now that we can purify full-length human P0, these findings can be explored in a more native-like setting needed for revealing molecular mechanisms in myelinogenesis and myelin disease.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbmem.2024.184368>.

Funding sources

The BiSS core facility has received infrastructure funding from the Research Council of Norway (RCN) through NORCRYST (grant number 245828) and NOR-OPENSREEN (grant number 245922). Research conducted at MAX IV, a Swedish national user facility, is supported by the Swedish Research Council under contract 2018-07152, the Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovation Systems under contract 2018-04969, and Formas under contract 2019-02496. Parts of the experiments carried out at ASTRID2 were under the support of the EU H2020 MOSBRI research and innovation program. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004806, MOSBRI transnational access proposal ID MOSBRI-2022-137. We acknowledge financial support from the University of Bergen (Norway) and several travel grants provided by BioCat, The Norwegian national graduate school in Biocatalysis. The work was supported by a research grant from the Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation (Finland), and the BIOPROM project is funded by the Research Council of Norway (project number 324877).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Oda C. Krokengen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christine Touma:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anna Mularski:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Aleksi Sutinen:** Investigation. **Ryan Dunkel:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Marie Ytterdal:** Investigation. **Arne Raasakka:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Haydyn D.T. Mertens:** Software, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Adam Cohen Simonsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Petri Kursula:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data will be publicly available online at zenodo.org at the time of publication.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the use of the Core Facility for Biophysics, Structural Biology, and Screening (BiSS) at the University of Bergen. In addition, we are grateful to the Molecular Imaging Center (MIC) at the Department of Biomedicine, University of Bergen, for providing access to instrumentation. We acknowledge MAX IV Laboratory for time on the Beamline CoSAXS under Proposal (ID 20220497/20200757). We gratefully acknowledge the synchrotron radiation facilities and the beamline support at ASTRID2. The assistance of Nikola C. Jones and Søren Vrønning Hoffman at the ASTRID2 synchrotron (Aarhus, Denmark) is highly appreciated. The authors would like to thank Diamond Light Source beamline B21 and principal beamline scientist Nathan Cowieson.

References

- [1] G. Jean Harry, A.D. Toews, Chapter 4- myelination, dysmyelination, and demyelination, in: W. Slikker, L.W. Chang (Eds.), *Handbook of Developmental Neurotoxicology*, Academic Press, San Diego, 1998, pp. 87–115.
- [2] D. Purves, G. Augustine, D. Fitzpatrick, et al., *Increased Conduction Velocity as a Result of Myelination*, Neuroscience, Sinauer Associates, Sunderland (MA), 2001.
- [3] S. Ruskamo, A. Raasakka, J.S. Pedersen, A. Martel, K. Skubnik, T. Darwish, L. Porcar, P. Kursula, Human myelin proteolipid protein structure and lipid bilayer stacking, *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* 79 (8) (2022) 419.
- [4] K.F. Mittendorf, J.T. Marinko, C.M. Hampton, Z. Ke, A. Hadziselimovic, J. P. Schleich, C.L. Law, J. Li, E.R. Wright, C.R. Sanders, M.D. Ohi, Peripheral myelin protein 22 alters membrane architecture, *Sci. Adv.* 3 (7) (2017) e1700220.
- [5] A. Raasakka, S. Ruskamo, J. Kowal, R. Barker, A. Baumann, A. Martel, J. Tuusa, M. Myllykoski, J. Bürck, A.S. Ulrich, H. Stahlberg, P. Kursula, Membrane association landscape of myelin basic protein portrays formation of the myelin major dense line, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (1) (2017) 4974.
- [6] S. Suresh, C. Wang, R. Nanekar, P. Kursula, J.M. Edwardson, Myelin basic protein and myelin protein 2 act synergistically to cause stacking of lipid bilayers, *Biochemistry* 49 (16) (2010) 3456–3463.
- [7] Y. Min, K. Kristiansen, J.M. Boggs, C. Husted, J.A. Zasadzinski, J. Israelachvili, Interaction forces and adhesion of supported myelin lipid bilayers modulated by myelin basic protein, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106 (9) (2009) 3154–3159.
- [8] M.T. Filbin, K. Zhang, W. Li, Y. Gao, Characterization of the effect on adhesion of different mutations in myelin (P0) protein, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 883 (1) (1999) 160–167.
- [9] A. Raasakka, S. Ruskamo, R. Barker, O.C. Krokengen, G.H. Vatne, C. K. Kristiansen, E.I. Hallin, M.W.A. Skoda, U. Bergmann, H. Wacklin-Knecht, N. C. Jones, S.V. Hoffmann, P. Kursula, Neuropathy-related mutations alter the membrane binding properties of the human myelin protein P0 cytoplasmic tail, *PLoS One* 14 (6) (2019) e0216833.
- [10] A. Raasakka, S. Ruskamo, J. Kowal, H. Han, A. Baumann, M. Myllykoski, A. Fasano, R. Rossano, P. Riccio, J. Bürck, A.S. Ulrich, H. Stahlberg, P. Kursula, Molecular structure and function of myelin protein P0 in membrane stacking, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1) (2019) 642.
- [11] M.H. Wong, M.T. Filbin, The cytoplasmic domain of the myelin P0 protein influences the adhesive interactions of its extracellular domain, *J. Cell Biol.* 126 (4) (1994) 1089–1097.
- [12] M.H. Wong, M.T. Filbin, Dominant-negative effect on adhesion by myelin P0 protein truncated in its cytoplasmic domain, *J. Cell Biol.* 134 (6) (1996) 1531–1541.
- [13] S. Ruskamo, O.C. Krokengen, J. Kowal, T. Nieminen, M. Lehtimäki, A. Raasakka, V.P. Dandey, I. Vattulainen, H. Stahlberg, P. Kursula, Cryo-EM, X-ray diffraction, and atomistic simulations reveal determinants for the formation of a supramolecular myelin-like proteolipid lattice, *J. Biol. Chem.* 295 (26) (2020) 8692–8705.
- [14] J. Sedzik, A.E. Blaurock, M. Hoehli, Reconstituted P2/myelin-lipid multilayers, *J. Neurochem.* 45 (3) (1985) 844–852.
- [15] M. Uusitalo, M.B. Klenow, S. Laulumaa, M.P. Blakeley, A.C. Simonsen, S. Ruskamo, P. Kursula, Human myelin protein P2: from crystallography to time-lapse membrane imaging and neuropathy-associated variants, *FEBS J.* 288 (23) (2021) 6716–6735.
- [16] S. Laulumaa, A. Raasakka, O.C. Krokengen, A. Safaryan, E.I. Hallin, et al., Structure and dynamics of a human myelin protein P2 portal region mutant indicate opening of the beta-barrel in fatty acid binding protein, *BMC Struct. Biol.* 18 (1) (2018).
- [17] D. D'Urso, P. Ehrhardt, H.W. Müller, Peripheral myelin protein 22 and protein zero: a novel association in peripheral nervous system myelin, *J. Neurosci.* 19 (9) (1999) 3396–3403.
- [18] H. Inouye, A.L. Ganser, D.A. Kirschner, Shiverer and normal peripheral myelin compared: basic protein localization, membrane interactions, and lipid composition, *J. Neurochem.* 45 (6) (1985) 1911–1922.
- [19] R. Martini, J. Zielasek, K.V. Toyka, K.P. Giese, M. Schachner, Protein zero (P0)-deficient mice show myelin degeneration in peripheral nerves characteristic of inherited human neuropathies, *Nat. Genet.* 11 (3) (1995) 281–286.
- [20] K.R. Jessen, R. Mirsky, Schwann cells and their precursors emerge as major regulators of nerve development, *Trends Neurosci.* 22 (9) (1999) 402–410.
- [21] D. D'Urso, P.J. Brophy, S.M. Staugaitis, C.S. Gillespie, A.B. Frey, J.G. Stempak, D. R. Colman, Protein zero of peripheral nerve myelin: biosynthesis, membrane insertion, and evidence for homotypic interaction, *Neuron* 4 (3) (1990) 449–460.
- [22] Z. Liu, Y. Wang, R.S. Yedidi, J.S. Brunzelle, I.A. Kovari, J. Sohi, J. Kamholz, L. C. Kovari, Crystal structure of the extracellular domain of human myelin protein zero, *Proteins* 80 (1) (2012) 307–313.
- [23] R.H. Quarles, Myelin sheaths: glycoproteins involved in their formation, maintenance and degeneration, *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* 59 (11) (2002) 1851–1871.
- [24] G. Lemke, R. Axel, Isolation and sequence of a cDNA encoding the major structural protein of peripheral myelin, *Cell* 40 (3) (1985) 501–508.
- [25] M.E. Shy, Peripheral neuropathies caused by mutations in the myelin protein zero, *J. Neurol. Sci.* 242 (1) (2006) 55–66.
- [26] O.A. Bizzozero, K. Fridal, A. Pastuszyn, Identification of the palmitoylation site in rat myelin P0 glycoprotein, *J. Neurochem.* 62 (3) (1994) 1163–1171.
- [27] M. Bharadwaj, O.A. Bizzozero, Myelin P0 glycoprotein and a synthetic peptide containing the palmitoylation site are both autoacylated, *J. Neurochem.* 65 (4) (1995) 1805–1815.
- [28] Y. Gao, W. Li, M.T. Filbin, Acylation of myelin P0 protein is required for adhesion, *J. Neurosci. Res.* 60 (6) (2000) 704–713.
- [29] P. Mandich, P. Fossa, S. Capponi, A. Geroldi, M. Acquaviva, R. Gulli, P. Ciotti, F. Manganelli, M. Grandis, E. Bellone, Clinical features and molecular modelling of novel MPZ mutations in demyelinating and axonal neuropathies, *Eur. J. Hum. Genet.* 17 (9) (2009) 1129–1134.
- [30] B.O. Choi, M.S. Lee, S.H. Shin, J.H. Hwang, K.G. Choi, W.K. Kim, I.N. Sunwoo, N. K. Kim, K.W. Chung, Mutational analysis of PMP22, MPZ, GJB1, EGR2 and NEFL in Korean Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy patients, *Hum. Mutat.* 24 (2) (2004) 185–186.
- [31] G.M. Fabrizi, M. Pellegrini, C. Angiari, T. Cavallaro, A. Morini, F. Taioli, I. Cabrini, D. Orrico, N. Rizzuto, Gene dosage sensitivity of a novel mutation in the intracellular domain of P0 associated with Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease type 1B, *Neuromuscul. Disord.* 16 (3) (2006) 183–187.
- [32] G. Miltenberger-Miltenyi, T. Schwarzbraun, W.N. Loscher, J. Wanschitz, C. Windpassinger, H.C. Duba, R. Seidl, G. Albrecht, H. Weirich-Schwaiger, H. Zoller, G. Utermann, M. Auer-Grumbach, A.R. Janneck, Identification and in silico analysis of 14 novel GJB1, MPZ and PMP22 gene mutations, *Eur. J. Hum. Genet.* 17 (9) (2009) 1154–1159.
- [33] V. Planté-Bordeneuve, Y. Parman, A. Guiochon-Mantel, Y. Alf, F. Deymeier, P. Serdaroglu, M. Eraksoy, G. Said, The range of chronic demyelinating neuropathy of infancy: a clinico-pathological and genetic study of 15 unrelated cases, *J. Neurol.* 248 (9) (2001) 795–803.
- [34] C. Schneider-Gold, J. Kötting, J.T. Epplen, R. Gold, W.M. Gerding, Unusual Charcot-Marie-Tooth phenotype due to a mutation within the intracellular domain of myelin protein zero, *Muscle Nerve* 41 (4) (2010) 550–554.
- [35] M.E. Shy, A. Jani, K. Krajewski, M. Grandis, R.A. Lewis, J. Li, R.R. Shy, J. Balsamo, J. Lilien, J.Y. Garbern, J. Kamholz, Phenotypic clustering in MPZ mutations, *Brain* 127 (Pt 2) (2004) 371–384.
- [36] V.A. Street, G. Meekins, H.P. Lipe, W.K. Seltzer, G.T. Carter, G.H. Kraft, T.D. Bird, Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy: clinical phenotypes of four novel mutations in the MPZ and Cx 32 genes, *Neuromuscul. Disord.* 12 (7–8) (2002) 643–650.
- [37] Y. Su, D.G. Brooks, L. Li, J. Lepercq, J.A. Trofatter, J.V. Ravetch, R.V. Lebo, Myelin protein zero gene mutated in Charcot-Marie-Tooth type 1B patients, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 90 (22) (1993) 10856–10860.
- [38] X. Luo, D. Sharma, H. Inouye, D. Lee, R.L. Avila, M. Salmons, D.A. Kirschner, Cytoplasmic domain of human myelin protein zero likely folded as beta-structure in compact myelin, *Biophys. J.* 92 (5) (2007) 1585–1597.
- [39] A. Akbarzadeh, R. Rezaei-Sadabady, S. Davaran, S.W. Joo, N. Zarghami, Y. Hanifepour, M. Samiei, M. Kouhi, K. Nejadi-Koshki, Liposome: classification, preparation, and applications, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 8 (1) (2013) 102.
- [40] A. Sharma, U.S. Sharma, Liposomes in drug delivery: progress and limitations, *Int. J. Pharm.* 154 (2) (1997) 123–140.
- [41] Y.H. Chan, S.G. Boxer, Model membrane systems and their applications, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* 11 (6) (2007) 581–587.
- [42] M. Eeman, M. Deleu, From biological membranes to biomimetic model membranes, *Biotechnol. Agron. Soc. Environ.* 14 (2010) 719–736.
- [43] R.S. Prosser, F. Evancic, J.L. Kitevski, M.S. Al-Abdul-Wahid, Current applications of bicelles in NMR studies of membrane-associated amphiphiles and proteins, *Biochemistry* 45 (28) (2006) 8453–8465.

- [44] U.H. Dürr, R. Soong, A. Ramamoorthy, When detergent meets bilayer: birth and coming of age of lipid bicelles, *Prog. Nucl. Magn. Reson. Spectrosc.* 69 (2013) 1–22.
- [45] R. Ujwal, J.U. Bowie, Crystallizing membrane proteins using lipidic bicelles, *Methods* 55 (4) (2011) 337–341.
- [46] T.N. Murugova, O.I. Ivankov, Y.L. Ryzhikau, D.V. Soloviov, K.V. Kovalev, D.V. Skachkova, A. Round, C. Baeken, A.V. Ishchenko, O.A. Volkov, A.V. Rogachev, A.V. Vlasov, A.I. Kuklin, V.I. Gordeliy, Mechanisms of membrane protein crystallization in ‘bicelles’, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (1) (2022) 11109.
- [47] L. Wang, F.J. Sigworth, Liposomes on a streptavidin crystal: a system to study membrane proteins by cryo-EM, *Methods Enzymol.* 481 (2010) 147–164.
- [48] X. Yao, X. Fan, N. Yan, Cryo-EM analysis of a membrane protein embedded in the liposome, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 117 (31) (2020) 18497–18503.
- [49] R. Dos Santos Morais, O. Delalande, J. Pérez, L. Mouret, A. Bondon, A. Martel, M.-S. Appavou, E. Le Rumeur, J.-F. Hubert, S. Combet, Contrast-matched isotropic bicelles: a versatile tool to specifically probe the solution structure of peripheral membrane proteins using SANS, *Langmuir* 33 (26) (2017) 6572–6580.
- [50] C.E. Conn, L. de Campo, A.E. Whitten, C.J. Garvey, A.M. Krause-Heuer, L. van't Hag, Membrane protein structures in lipid bilayers; small-angle neutron scattering with contrast-matched bicontinuous cubic phases, *Front. Chem.* 8 (2020) 619470.
- [51] H.G. Sebinelli, I.A. Borin, P. Ciancaglini, M. Bolean, Topographical and mechanical properties of liposome surfaces harboring Na,K-ATPase by means of atomic force microscopy, *Soft Matter* 15 (13) (2019) 2737–2745.
- [52] J.H. Borrell, M.T. Montero, A. Morros, O. Domènech, Unspecific membrane protein–lipid recognition: combination of AFM imaging, force spectroscopy, DSC and FRET measurements, *J. Mol. Recognit.* 28 (11) (2015) 679–686.
- [53] M. Kahnt, K. Klementiev, V. Haghighat, C. Weninger, T.S. Plivelic, A.E. Terry, A. Björling, Measurement of the coherent beam properties at the CoSAXS beamline, *J. Synchrotron Radiat.* 28 (2021) 1948–1953.
- [54] K. Manalastas-Cantos, P.V. Konarev, N.R. Hajizadeh, A.G. Kikhney, M. V. Petoukhov, D.S. Molodenskiy, A. Panjkovich, H.D.T. Mertens, A. Gruzinov, C. Borges, C.M. Jeffries, D.I. Svergun, D. Franke, ATSAS 3.0: expanded functionality and new tools for small-angle scattering data analysis, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 54 (Pt 1) (2021) 343–355.
- [55] P. Hägerbäumer, F. Gräbitz-Bräuer, M. Annegarn, C. Dargel, T.J. Stank, T. Bizien, T. Hellweg, Interactions between DMPC model membranes, the drug naproxen, and the saponin β -aescin, *Pharmaceutics* 15 (2) (2023).
- [56] N.P. Cowieson, C.J.C. Edwards-Gayle, K. Inoue, N.S. Khunti, J. Douth, E. Williams, S. Daniels, G. Preece, N.A. Krumpa, J.P. Sutter, M.D. Tully, N. J. Terrill, R.P. Rambo, Beamline B21: high-throughput small-angle X-ray scattering at diamond light source, *J. Synchrotron Radiat.* 27 (2020) 1438–1446.
- [57] G. Tria, H.D. Mertens, M. Kachala, D.I. Svergun, Advanced ensemble modelling of flexible macromolecules using X-ray solution scattering, *IUCr* 2 (Pt 2) (2015) 207–217.
- [58] D.I. Svergun, M.V. Petoukhov, M.H. Koch, Determination of domain structure of proteins from X-ray solution scattering, *Biophys. J.* 80 (6) (2001) 2946–2953.
- [59] M.V. Petoukhov, D. Franke, A.V. Shkumatov, G. Tria, A.G. Kikhney, M. Gajda, C. Gorba, H.D. Mertens, P.V. Konarev, D.I. Svergun, New developments in the ATSAS program package for small-angle scattering data analysis, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 45 (Pt 2) (2012) 342–350.
- [60] B.R. Brooks, C.L. Brooks 3rd, A.D. Mackerell Jr., L. Nilsson, R.J. Petrella, B. Roux, Y. Won, G. Archontis, C. Bartels, S. Boresch, A. Caffisch, L. Caves, Q. Cui, A. R. Dinner, M. Feig, S. Fischer, J. Gao, M. Hodoscek, W. Im, K. Kuczera, T. Lazaridis, J. Ma, V. Ovchinnikov, E. Paci, R.W. Pastor, C.B. Post, J.Z. Pu, M. Schaefer, B. Tidor, R.M. Venable, H.L. Woodcock, X. Wu, W. Yang, D.M. York, M. Karplus, CHARMM: the biomolecular simulation program, *J. Comput. Chem.* 30 (10) (2009) 1545–1614.
- [61] W.L. DeLano, Pymol: an open-source molecular graphics tool, *CCP4 News*, *Protein Crystallogr.* 40 (1) (2002) 82–92.
- [62] J. Jumper, R. Evans, A. Pritzel, T. Green, M. Figurnov, O. Ronneberger, K. Tunyasuvunakool, R. Bates, A. Židek, A. Potapenko, A. Bridgland, C. Meyer, S. A.A. Kohl, A.J. Ballard, A. Cowie, B. Romera-Paredes, S. Nikolov, R. Jain, J. Adler, T. Back, S. Petersen, D. Reiman, E. Clancy, M. Zielinski, M. Steinegger, M. Pacholska, T. Berghammer, S. Bodenstein, D. Silver, O. Vinyals, A.W. Senior, K. Kavukcuoglu, P. Kohli, D. Hassabis, Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold, *Nature* 596 (7873) (2021) 583–589.
- [63] M. Mirdita, K. Schütze, Y. Moriwaki, L. Heo, S. Ovchinnikov, M. Steinegger, ColabFold: making protein folding accessible to all, *Nat. Methods* 19 (6) (2022) 679–682.
- [64] J.B. Hopkins, R.E. Gillilan, S. Skou, BioXTAS RAW: improvements to a free open-source program for small-angle X-ray scattering data reduction and analysis, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 50 (Pt 5) (2017) 1545–1553.
- [65] T.D. Grant, Ab initio electron density determination directly from solution scattering data, *Nat. Methods* 15 (3) (2018) 191–193.
- [66] R. Sreij, C. Dargel, P. Geisler, Y. Hertle, A. Radulescu, S. Pasini, J. Perez, L. H. Moleiro, T. Hellweg, DMPC vesicle structure and dynamics in the presence of low amounts of the saponin aescin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 20 (14) (2018) 9070–9083.
- [67] C. Courreges, F. Nallet, E.J. Dufourc, R. Oda, Unprecedented observation of days-long remnant orientation of phospholipid bicelles: a small-angle X-ray scattering and theoretical study, *Langmuir* 27 (15) (2011) 9122–9130.
- [68] M. Li, H.H. Morales, J. Katsaras, N. Kučerka, Y. Yang, P.M. Macdonald, M.-P. Nieh, Morphological characterization of DMPC/CHAPSO bicellar mixtures: a combined SANS and NMR study, *Langmuir* 29 (51) (2013) 15943–15957.
- [69] M. Beaugrand, A.A. Arnold, J. Hénin, D.E. Warschawski, P.T.F. Williamson, I. Marcotte, Lipid concentration and molar ratio boundaries for the use of isotropic bicelles, *Langmuir* 30 (21) (2014) 6162–6170.
- [70] R.D. Giudice, N. Paracini, T. Laursen, C. Blanchet, F. Roosen-Runge, M. Cárdenas, Expanding the toolbox for bicelle-forming surfactant-lipid mixtures, *Molecules* 27 (21) (2022) 7628.
- [71] J. Katsaras, T.A. Harroun, J. Pencer, M.-P. Nieh, ‘Bicellar’ lipid mixtures as used in biochemical and biophysical studies, *Naturwissenschaften* 92 (8) (2005) 355–366.
- [72] Y. Poitelon, A.M. Kopec, S. Belin, Myelin fat facts: an overview of lipids and fatty acid metabolism, *Cells* 9 (4) (2020).
- [73] J.T. Marinko, H. Huang, W.D. Penn, J.A. Capra, J.P. Schleich, C.R. Sanders, Folding and misfolding of human membrane proteins in health and disease: from single molecules to cellular proteostasis, *Chem. Rev.* 119 (9) (2019) 5537–5606.
- [74] H. Hong, Toward understanding driving forces in membrane protein folding, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* 564 (2014) 297–313.
- [75] K. Corin, J.U. Bowie, How physical forces drive the process of helical membrane protein folding, *EMBO Rep.* 23 (3) (2022) e53025.
- [76] K. Corin, J.U. Bowie, How bilayer properties influence membrane protein folding, *Protein Sci.* 29 (12) (2020) 2348–2362.
- [77] A. Raasakka, N.C. Jones, S.V. Hoffmann, P. Kursula, Ionic strength and calcium regulate membrane interactions of myelin basic protein and the cytoplasmic domain of myelin protein zero, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 511 (1) (2019) 7–12.
- [78] S. Ruskamo, R.P. Yadav, S. Sharma, M. Lehtimäki, S. Laulumaa, S. Aggarwal, M. Simons, J. Bürck, A.S. Ulrich, A.H. Juffer, I. Kursula, P. Kursula, Atomic resolution view into the structure-function relationships of the human myelin peripheral membrane protein P2, *Acta Crystallogr. D Biol. Crystallogr.* 70 (Pt 1) (2014) 165–176.
- [79] G. Campi, M.D. Gioacchino, N. Poccia, A.M.V. Ricci, M. Burghammer, A. Bianconi, Intrinsic Dynamical Fluctuations of PNS Myelin, 2017.
- [80] N. Li, S. Perutkova, M. Rappolt, My first electron density map: a beginner's guide to small angle X-ray diffraction, *Elektrotehniski Vestnik/Electrotech. Rev.* 84 (2017).
- [81] S.-H. Lin, G. Guidotti, Chapter 35 purification of membrane proteins, in: R. R. Burgess, M.P. Deutscher (Eds.), *Methods in Enzymology*, Academic Press, 2009, pp. 619–629.
- [82] L. Shapiro, J.P. Doyle, P. Hensley, D.R. Colman, W.A. Hendrickson, Crystal structure of the extracellular domain from P0, the major structural protein of peripheral nerve myelin, *Neuron* 17 (3) (1996) 435–449.
- [83] O.C. Krokengen, A. Raasakka, P. Kursula, The intrinsically disordered protein glue of the myelin major dense line: linking AlphaFold2 predictions to experimental data, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 34 (2023) 101474.
- [84] P. Eastman, J. Swails, J.D. Chodera, R.T. McGibbon, Y. Zhao, K.A. Beauchamp, L.-P. Wang, A.C. Simmonett, M.P. Harrigan, C.D. Stern, R.P. Wiewiora, B.R. Brooks, V.S. Pande, OpenMM 7: rapid development of high performance algorithms for molecular dynamics, *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 13 (7) (2017) e1005659.
- [85] G. Tesei, K. Lindorff-Larsen, Improved predictions of phase behaviour of intrinsically disordered proteins by tuning the interaction range [version 2; peer review: 2 approved], *Open Res. Europe* 2 (94) (2023).
- [86] G. Tesei, A.I. Trolle, N. Jonsson, J. Betz, F.E. Knudsen, F. Pesce, K.E. Johansson, K. Lindorff-Larsen, Conformational ensembles of the human intrinsically disordered proteome, *Nature* 626 (8000) (2024) 897–904.
- [87] A. Kister, I. Kister, Overview of myelin, major myelin lipids, and myelin-associated proteins, *Front. Chem.* 10 (2023).
- [88] A. Raasakka, P. Kursula, How does protein zero assemble compact myelin? *Cells* 9 (8) (2020) 1832.
- [89] V. Prada, M. Passalacqua, M. Bono, P. Luzzi, S. Scazzola, L.A. Nobbio, S. Capponi, E. Bellone, P. Mandich, G. Mancardi, M. Shy, A. Schenone, M. Grandis, Gain of glycosylation: a new pathomechanism of myelin protein zero mutations, *Ann. Neurol.* 71 (3) (2012) 427–431.
- [90] J. Eichberg, Myelin P0: new knowledge and new roles, *Neurochem. Res.* 27 (11) (2002) 1331–1340.
- [91] M.L. Plotkowski, S. Kim, M.L. Phillips, A.W. Partridge, C.M. Deber, J.U. Bowie, Trans-membrane domain of myelin protein zero can form dimers: possible implications for myelin construction, *Biochemistry* 46 (43) (2007) 12164–12173.
- [92] W.T. Norton, S.E. Poduslo, Myelination in rat brain: changes in myelin composition during brain maturation, *J. Neurochem.* 21 (4) (1973) 759–773.
- [93] B. Garbay, A.M. Heape, F. Sargueil, C. Cassagne, Myelin synthesis in the peripheral nervous system, *Prog. Neurobiol.* 61 (3) (2000) 267–304.
- [94] H. Ozgen, W. Baron, D. Hoekstra, N. Kahya, Oligodendroglial membrane dynamics in relation to myelin biogenesis, *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* 73 (17) (2016) 3291–3310.
- [95] G. Saher, B. Brugger, C. Lappe-Siefke, W. Mobius, R. Tozawa, M.C. Wehr, F. Wieland, S. Ishibashi, K.A. Nave, High cholesterol level is essential for myelin membrane growth, *Nat. Neurosci.* 8 (4) (2005) 468–475.
- [96] G. Saher, S. Quintes, W. Mobius, M.C. Wehr, E.M. Kramer-Albers, B. Brugger, K. A. Nave, Cholesterol regulates the endoplasmic reticulum exit of the major membrane protein P0 required for peripheral myelin compaction, *J. Neurosci.* 29 (19) (2009) 6094–6104.
- [97] G. Saher, M. Simons, Cholesterol and myelin biogenesis, *Subcell. Biochem.* 51 (2010) 489–508.
- [98] C.V. Kulkarni, W. Wachter, G. Iglesias-Salto, S. Engelskirchen, S. Ahualli, Monoolein: a magic lipid? *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 13 (8) (2011) 3004–3021.

- [99] D. Lombardo, M.A. Kiselev, S. Magazù, P. Calandra, Amphiphiles self-assembly: basic concepts and future perspectives of supramolecular approaches, *Adv. Condens. Matter Phys.* 2015 (2015) 151683.
- [100] A. Bilalov, U. Olsson, B. Lindman, Complexation between DNA and surfactants and lipids: phase behavior and molecular organization, *Soft Matter* 8 (43) (2012) 11022–11033.
- [101] B. de Kruijff, P.R. Cullis, The influence of poly(L-lysine) on phospholipid polymorphism evidence that electrostatic polypeptide-phospholipid interactions can modulate bilayer/ non-bilayer transitions, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Biomembr.* 601 (1980) 235–240.
- [102] B. de Kruijff, P.R. Cullis, Cytochrome c specifically induces non-bilayer structures in cardiolipin-containing model membranes, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 602 (3) (1980) 477–490.
- [103] N.-W. Hsu, B. Nouri, L.-T. Chen, H.-L. Chen, Hexagonal close-packed sphere phase of conformationally symmetric block copolymer, *Macromolecules* 53 (21) (2020) 9665–9675.
- [104] L.-T. Chen, C.-Y. Chen, H.-L. Chen, FCC or HCP: the stable close-packed lattice of crystallographically equivalent spherical micelles in block copolymer/ homopolymer blend, *Polymer* 169 (2019) 131–137.
- [105] D. Carrier, M. Pézolet, Raman spectroscopic study of the interaction of poly-L-lysine with dipalmitoylphosphatidylglycerol bilayers, *Biophys. J.* 46 (4) (1984) 497–506.
- [106] J.M. Boggs, D. Stamp, M.A. Moscarello, Interaction of myelin basic protein with dipalmitoylphosphatidylglycerol: dependence on the lipid phase and investigation of a metastable state, *Biochemistry* 20 (21) (1981) 6066–6072.
- [107] F. Natali, A. Gliozzi, R. Rolandi, A. Relini, P. Cavatorta, A. Deriu, A. Fasano, P. Riccio, Changes in the anisotropy of oriented membrane dynamics induced by myelin basic protein, *Appl. Phys. A* 74 (1) (2002) s1582–s1584.
- [108] M. Rappolt, A. Hinkel, F. Bringezu, K. Lohner, Mechanism of the lamellar/inverse hexagonal phase transition examined by high resolution X-ray diffraction, *Biophys. J.* 84 (5) (2003) 3111–3122.
- [109] R. Shaharabani, M. Ram-On, R. Avineri, R. Aharoni, R. Arnon, Y. Talmon, R. Beck, Structural transition in myelin membrane as initiator of multiple sclerosis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 138 (37) (2016) 12159–12165.
- [110] R. Shaharabani, M. Ram-On, Y. Talmon, R. Beck, Pathological transitions in myelin membranes driven by environmental and multiple sclerosis conditions, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 115 (44) (2018) 11156–11161.
- [111] L. Wrabetz, M.L. Feltri, A. Quattrini, D. Imperiale, S. Previtali, M. D'Antonio, R. Martini, X. Yin, B.D. Trapp, L. Zhou, S.Y. Chiu, A. Messing, P(0) glycoprotein overexpression causes congenital hypomyelination of peripheral nerves, *J. Cell Biol.* 148 (5) (2000) 1021–1034.
- [112] K.-A. Nave, O. Boespflug-Tanguy, X-linked developmental defects of myelination: from mouse mutants to human genetic diseases, *Neuroscientist* 2 (1) (1996) 33–43.
- [113] A. Robaglia-Schlupp, J. Pizant, J.C. Norreel, E. Passage, D. Sabéran-Djoneidi, J. L. Ansaldo, L. Vinay, D. Figarella-Branger, N. Lévy, F. Clarac, P. Cau, J. F. Pellissier, M. Fontés, PMP22 overexpression causes dysmyelination in mice, *Brain* 125 (10) (2002) 2213–2221.
- [114] I. Callegari, C. Gemelli, A. Geroldi, F. Veneri, P. Mandich, M. D'Antonio, D. Pareyson, M.E. Shy, A. Schenone, V. Prada, M. Grandis, Mutation update for myelin protein zero-related neuropathies and the increasing role of variants causing a late-onset phenotype, *J. Neurol.* 266 (11) (2019) 2629–2645.
- [115] Y. Bai, X. Wu, K.M. Brennan, D.S. Wang, M. D'Antonio, J. Moran, J. Svaren, M. E. Shy, Myelin protein zero mutations and the unfolded protein response in Charcot Marie Tooth disease type 1B, *Ann. Clin. Transl. Neurol.* 5 (4) (2018) 445–455.
- [116] F. Blanquet-Grossard, D. Pham-Dinh, A. Dautigny, P. Latour, C. Bonnebouche, P. Diraison, F. Chapon, G. Chazot, A. Vandenberghe, Charcot-Marie-Tooth type 1B neuropathy: a mutation at the single glycosylation site in the major peripheral myelin glycoprotein Po, *Hum. Mutat.* 8 (2) (1996) 185–186.
- [117] R.L. Avila, M. D'Antonio, A. Bachi, H. Inouye, M.L. Feltri, L. Wrabetz, D. A. Kirschner, P0 (protein zero) mutation S34C underlies instability of internodal myelin in S63C mice, *J. Biol. Chem.* 285 (53) (2010) 42001–42012.
- [118] H. Chen, C.J. Kusk, C.M. Tuck-Muller, J.E. Martinez, R.D. Dorand, W. Wertelecki, Confirmation of proximal 1q duplication using fluorescence in situ hybridization, *Am. J. Med. Genet.* 50 (1) (1994) 28–31.
- [119] M.H. Maeda, J. Mitsui, B.-W. Soong, Y. Takahashi, H. Ishiura, S. Hayashi, Y. Shirota, Y. Ichikawa, H. Matsumoto, M. Arai, T. Okamoto, S. Miyama, J. Shimizu, J. Inazawa, J. Goto, S. Tsuji, Increased gene dosage of myelin protein zero causes Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease, *Ann. Neurol.* 71 (1) (2012) 84–92.
- [120] N. Mizuno, J. Varkey, N.C. Kegulian, B.G. Hegde, N. Cheng, R. Langen, A. C. Steven, Remodeling of lipid vesicles into cylindrical micelles by alpha-synuclein in an extended alpha-helical conformation, *J. Biol. Chem.* 287 (35) (2012) 29301–29311.
- [121] T.L. Boye, J.C. Jeppesen, K. Maeda, W. Pezeshkian, V. Solovyeva, J. Nylandsted, A.C. Simonsen, Annexins induce curvature on free-edge membranes displaying distinct morphologies, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1) (2018) 10309.
- [122] M. Berg Klenow, C. Iversen, F. Wendelboe Lund, A. Mularski, A.S. Busk Heitmann, C. Dias, J. Nylandsted, A.C. Simonsen, Annexins A1 and A2 accumulate and are immobilized at cross-linked membrane-membrane interfaces, *Biochemistry* 60 (16) (2021) 1248–1259.
- [123] D.M. Halaby, J.P. Mornon, The immunoglobulin superfamily: an insight on its tissular, species, and functional diversity, *J. Mol. Evol.* 46 (4) (1998) 389–400.
- [124] H. Inouye, D.A. Kirschner, Evolution of myelin ultrastructure and the major structural myelin proteins, *Brain Res.* 1641 (Pt A) (2016) 43–63.
- [125] E. Sorour, J. MacMillan, M. Upadhyaya, Novel mutation of the myelin P0 gene in a CMT1B family, *Hum. Mutat.* 9 (1) (1997) 74–77.
- [126] N. Hattori, M. Yamamoto, T. Yoshihara, H. Koike, M. Nakagawa, H. Yoshikawa, A. Ohnishi, K. Hayasaka, O. Onodera, M. Baba, H. Yasuda, T. Saito, K. Nakashima, J. Kira, R. Kaji, N. Oka, G. Sobue, Demyelinating and axonal features of Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease with mutations of myelin-related proteins (PMP22, MPZ and Cx32): a clinicopathological study of 205 Japanese patients, *Brain* 126 (Pt 1) (2003) 134–151.
- [127] M. Grandis, T. Vigo, M. Passalacqua, M. Jain, S. Scazzola, V. La Padula, M. Brucal, F. Benvenuto, L. Nobbio, A. Cadoni, G.L. Mancardi, J. Kamholz, M.E. Shy, A. Schenone, Different cellular and molecular mechanisms for early and late-onset myelin protein zero mutations, *Hum. Mol. Genet.* 17 (13) (2008) 1877–1889.
- [128] S. Kim, T.-J. Jeon, A. Oberai, D. Yang, J.J. Schmidt, J.U. Bowie, Transmembrane glycine zippers: physiological and pathological roles in membrane proteins, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 102 (40) (2005) 14278–14283.